

TREASoURcE

D9.3 Joint CCRI deliverable 2

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Acronyms and abbreviations

Acronym	Full name
BT	Business Tampere
CCRI	Circular Cities and Regions Initiative
CDP	Communication and Dissemination Plan
CE	Circular Economy
CLIC	CLIC Innovation Ltd
CSS	Circular Systemic Solution
D	Deliverable report
DMP	Data Management Plan
ECO	ECO STOR AS
EKOF	Ekokumppanit Oy (EcoFellows)
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
Frstad	Fredrikstad kommune
FVH	Forum Virium Helsinki Oy
GA	Grant Agreement
GD	GreenDelta GMBH
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KVC	Key value chain
KVC-DEMO	Key value chain demonstration
MTK	The Central Union of Agricultural Producers and Forest Owners
OFK	Østfold Fylkeskommune (Previously Viken)
PF	Polyfuels Group AB (Previously known as Green Ideas Group GIG)
SDU	Syddansk Universitet
SE	Stakeholder engagement
SE-DEMO	Stakeholder engagement demonstration
SINTEF	SINTEF AS / SINTEF Energy
TalTech	Tallinna Tehnikaülikool
TARTU	Tartu Linn (Tartu City)
TLN	Tallinna Linn (City of Tallinn)
VIKEN	Viken Fylkeskommune
VTT	VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd

Executive Summary

This deliverable outlines the activities of the TREASoURcE project relating to the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI) and the Thematic Working Groups (TWG), as well as collaboration established with other CCRI-projects, and CCRI Pilots and Fellows. It also provides a summary of the policy recommendations developed through the TREASoURcE project. This is the second of three deliverables in this topic, the deliverable is always updated for each of the project periods (period 1 M1-M18; period 2 M19-M36; period 3 M37-M48).

Building on our engagement in Period 1, TREASoURcE continued its active involvement in CCRI activities coordinated by the CCRI Coordination and Support Office (CCRI-CSO) throughout Period 2. This included participation in 10 CCRI-related events and activities. Collaboration with Finnish CCRI Pilots and Fellows—particularly the Tampere - Pirkanmaa region - was sustained during this period. In total, 26 project collaborations were established, alongside partnerships with 11 associations or networks. TREASoURcE has also established collaborations with the following CCRI Pilots and Fellows: Helsinki-Uusimaa Circular Valley and Helsinki-Uusimaa region (Finland), Tampere region (Finland), and city of Berlin (Germany), Asker municipality (Norway), and Møre og Romsdal county (Norway). In addition, several other cities, municipalities and regions and their local stakeholders have been collaborated with outside the CCRI network, for example Tartu (Estonia), Tallinn (Estonia), Riga (Latvia), Kaunas (Lithuania), Warsaw (Poland), Lempäälä (Finland), Turku (Finland), Salo (Finland), Forssa (Finland), Hämeenkyrö (Finland), Mänttä-Vilppula (Finland), Orivesi (Finland), Urjala (Finland), Satakunta region (Finland), Jyväskylä region (Finland), Sotkamo (Finland), Häme region (Finland), and from Norway: Kongsberg, Flå, Indre Østfold, Rakkestad, Spydeberg, Marker, Nordre Follo, Lier, Ringerike, Vestby, Drammen, Nittedal, Bærum, Aurskog-Høland, and Nannestad.

TREASoURcE has actively contributed to 3 Thematic Working Groups (TWGs) hosted by the CCRI-CSO, focusing on circular resource management, industrial symbiosis and circular economy in industries, and circular bioeconomy. This included participation in 12 TWG meetings and workshops. Key activities involved engaging in TWG sessions, sharing expected project outputs and experiences as part of peer-to-peer learning, and delivering project-related presentations.

Policy recommendations have been actively developed across multiple work packages within the TREASoURcE project to support circular economy transitions. WP1 delivered a comprehensive analysis of EU and national regulatory frameworks, Deliverable D1.3, “Legislative and Regulatory Framework for Target Value Chains, resulting in a total 16 targeted policy recommendations, 8 for plastic, 5 for EV batteries, and 3 for bio-based side and waste streams, complemented by a policy brief on Finnish biogas incentives. WP2 contributed regional-level policy recommendations, including guidance on climate-smart public procurement (biogas and circular plastics) in Østfold and circular economy strategies across 51 municipalities. WP4 provided recommendations on accelerating second-life battery uptake in the stationary energy market, published in both Deliverable D4.1 and a scientific journal article.

1. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable outlines the activities of the TREASoURcE project relating to the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI) and the Thematic Working Groups (TWG) as well as collaboration established with other CCRI-projects, and CCRI Pilots and Fellows. It also provides a summary of the policy recommendations developed through the TREASoURcE project. This is the second of three deliverables under this topic, and it is updated for each project period: Period 1 (M1–M18), Period 2 (M19–M36), and Period 3 (M37–M48).

The CCRI is an initiative of the European Commission, launched by the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation as part of the EU Circular Economy Action Plan 2020. It contributes to the policy objectives of the EU Green Deal, including the 2050 climate neutrality target, and the EU Bioeconomy Strategy. The CCRI is funded by Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe, the EU's research, and innovation framework programmes. TREASoURcE has received funding from the Horizon Europe programme. The aim of the initiative is to combine knowledge sharing, technical and financial support, the initiative assists stakeholders across Europe's cities and regions, including regional and local authorities, industry representatives, research and technology organisations and civil society (European Commission, 2023).

The CCRI-projects are part of the multi-stakeholder collaboration and support scheme. The aim of the CCRI-projects is to demonstrate circular systemic solutions (CSS) and to test circular business and governance models. TREASoURcE is focusing on developing systemic circular solutions that are a combination of the key value chain demonstrations (KVC-DEMOS, technical part of the project) and stakeholder engagement demonstrations (SE-DEMOS). We actively seek to share as openly as possible the work, methodologies, learnings, and results of our project. All possible outputs will be uploaded to the TREASoURcE Replication Handbook. It is a central platform for the project to upload all possible exploitable and replicable results to be accessible to all.

2. CCRI collaboration

2.1. Collaboration with CCRI, CCRI-CSO, CCRI Projects, CCRI Pilots and Fellows

TREASoURcE has been actively involved in the CCRI activities organised by the CCRI-CSO throughout its second period. Participation in 10 different CCRI related activities and events (CLIC, VTT, BT), involvement in CCRI's 3 thematic working groups (CLIC, VTT, MTK, BT), participation in 12 different TWG meetings and workshops. Collaboration with the Finnish CCRI Pilots and Fellows, notably with the Tampere - Pirkanmaa region, has continued in P2.

Several materials have been shared with the CCRI-CSO for enhanced communication and dissemination. The invitation and programme of the mid-term results webinar in May 2024 was shared to be disseminated through the CCRI newsletter for enhanced visibility among the CCRI stakeholders with a direct interest towards TREASoURcE results. Furthermore, a comprehensive set of publicly available materials including links has been communicated to CCRI-CSO for publication under the knowledge materials section on the CCRI website. These materials included published reports, scientific papers and theses, a policy brief, Replication Handbook and materials and recordings from public webinars organised by TREASoURcE (17 items in total). Additionally, a success story article on the KiertoaSuomesta.fi marketplace was prepared and sent for publication. A next set of materials will be sent once more published materials have been accumulated, coordinated by CLIC.

TREASoURcE project, activities and outputs have been highlighted in the following CCRI newsletters and articles on the CCRI website:

- February 2024 newsletter: Meet the CCRI stakeholders: TREASoURcE (CCRI Project). An interview with Anna Tenhunen-Lunkka. ([link](#))
- May 2024 newsletter: Invitation to the TREASoURcE mid-term results webinar 'Local circular economy solutions to global challenges – Exclusive look at the first results from TREASoURcE demos' with registration link. ([link](#))
- July 2024 newsletter: "A guide to circular economy models": dissemination of the Replication Handbook with a link to the website. ([link](#))
- Interview: Meet the CCRI stakeholders: TREASoURcE (CCRI Project). Website article published on 05.02.2024. ([link](#))
- Webinar: Local circular economy solutions to global challenges – Exclusive look at the first results from TREASoURcE demos. CCRI Event calendar entry published in May 2024. ([link](#))

Activities and highlights from the CCRI community have been included in TREASoURcE newsletters whenever relevant. Various activities and events have been promoted in the following issues:

- March 2024 newsletter ([link](#))
- June 2024 newsletter ([link](#))
- September 2024 newsletter ([link](#))

Furthermore, social media posts by the CCRI have been liked and shared actively, and whenever relevant, through TREASoURcE LinkedIn account.

The planning of the Joint CCRI projects' video has been started with an interactive session with WP8 and WP2 team members as participants, led by CLIC. Ideas on potential topics and collaboration projects were mapped. After discussions with two CCRI-projects, a continued collaboration with [CircleUp](#) has been confirmed. A joint brainstorming session with TREASoURcE and CircleUp representatives has been held to further ideate and develop the topics. Partners from CLIC, EKOF, MTK, OFK and BT participated the session. The video is expected to be finalised and disseminated in the autumn 2025.

TREASoURcE has also established active collaborations with the following CCRI Pilots and Fellows: Helsinki-Uusimaa Circular Valley and Helsinki-Uusimaa region (Finland), Tampere region (Finland), and city of Berlin (Germany), Asker municipality (Norway), and Møre og Romsdal county (Norway). We have organised several events where the Pilot and Fellows have been invited to, and many times have held presentations.

List of main CCRI activities in Period 2 (P2), TWG participation reported in the next chapter:

1. 4.4.2024 Participation in CCRI 6th Webinar| Stimulating synergies between circular economy and climate action (BT)
2. 18.4.2024 Attendance to CCRI, OECD and EIB accelerator session 'Cities & regions getting ahead with the circular transition' at WCEF (VTT, CLIC, BT)
3. 30.4.2024 Participation in 2nd CCRI Associated Partners online workshop on 'Involvement of the private sector in circular economy and Circular Systemic Solutions' (BT)
4. 13.11.2024 Participation in the CCRI Coordination and Support Workshop in Brussels (VTT, CLIC, BT)
5. 16.1.2025 From demonstration to deployment of circular solutions: First lessons learnt from CCRI pilot cases workshop attendance, presenting TREASoURcE activities and lessons learnt (VTT, CLIC)
6. 4.2.2025 Tehdassaari (CirEco) and DENIFINITE-CCRI funding sparring with BT funding experts
7. 12.2.2025 Meeting with Tugce Tugran to plan TREASoURcE's contribution to the Circular Resource Management TWG Meeting on 27.3.2025 (VTT, CLIC)
8. 20.3.2025 Participation in CCRI Circular Investing: Pitching Investment Opportunities for Circular Solutions (BT, CLIC)
9. 20.3.2025 Partial participation in Call for Interest by the CCRI Communities of Practice Q&A session (BT)
10. 21.5.2025 Participation in the first CCRI Community of Practice (CoP) on Supporting Local Circular Businesses online meeting (BT)

2.2. Thematic Working Groups

TREASoURcE has been active in three Thematic Working Groups hosted by the CCRI Coordination and Support Office (CCRI-CSO): circular resource management, industrial symbiosis and circular economy in industries, as well as circular bioeconomy. The following persons have been included in the TWGs:

- *Circular Bioeconomy*: Kaisa Simola, Riina Kärki, Nora Berglund (MTK, Riina leads the KVC work package WP5 bio-based side and waste streams; Nora substituting during her parental leave)
- *Circular Resource Management*: Kaisa Simola, Pirkko Eteläaho (from BT, Pirkko leads the circular business, exploitation, and funding-related matters)
- *Industrial symbiosis and CE in industries*: Pirkko Eteläaho, Kaisa Simola, Tiina Laiho (CLIC, Tiina led the work and demonstrations related to symbiotic B2B partnerships until 8/2024)

In Period 2, main activities include the participation in the Thematic Working Group sessions, sharing actively the expected outputs and giving project related presentations. In Period 3, TREASoURcE will continue to actively participate the CCRI and TWG activities.

The participation in the following TWG meetings in P2:

1. 7.3.2024 CCRI thematic working group preparation meeting (BT and CLIC)
2. 14.3.2024 CCRI thematic working group workshop on industrial symbiosis (BT and CLIC)
3. 22.3.2024 CCRI TWG meeting on Circular Bioeconomy (MTK)
4. 22.5. CCRI TWG Meeting on Industrial Symbiosis: presenting TREASoURcE / Tampere Region good practices (BT)
5. 31.5.2024 Participation in CCRI | 5th TWG meeting on Circular Bioeconomy (MTK)
6. 13.11.2024 Participation to the DEFINITE-CCRI investor panel in Brussels (BT)
7. 13.11.2024 Participation in CCRI TWG meeting on Circular Bioeconomy (CLIC)
8. 13.11.2024 Participation in CCRI TWG meeting on Circular Resource management (VTT, CLIC)
9. 28.11.2024 CCRI first discussion event regarding joint ideation on future co-operation possibilities on plastics, CO2 and bioresources (BT, Ecofellows and Päijät-Häme Region)
10. 12.3.2025 Participation in CCRI | 1st TWG C-BIO workshop of 2025 (MTK)
11. 19.3.2025 Participation in CCRI | 7th TWG Meeting on Industrial Symbiosis and CE in Industries, presenting also our ongoing Horizon planning status (BT, Ecofellows and Päijät-Häme Region)
12. 27.3.2025 Participation in CCRI TWG meeting on Circular Resource Management, presenting TREASoURcE repair and reuse activities (VTT, OFK, EKOF, Frstad, Tartu, CLIC)

3. Collaboration with other projects, networks, and regions

In total, TREASoURcE has collaborated with 26 projects, 11 networks, and 32 regions/cities/municipalities.

Collaboration with other projects in P2:

1. Collaboration with the Norwegian nationally funded project SafeBESS through organization of a common 18.1.2024
2. FER-PLAY:
 - Meeting 8.5.2024 (MTK, CLIC, EKOF)
 - 2nd working group 4.9.2024, presentation about digital marketplace (MTK, BT)
3. eMuovi:
 - Steering group meetings: 13.12.2023, 17.4.2024, 5.9.2024 18.12.2024 and 12.3.2025 (MTK)
 - Presentation about marketplace in final webinar 12.12.2024 (MTK)
4. Muutosvoimaa tulevaan - project
 - Collaboration on Circular Economy Christmas Calendars in 2023 and 2024 (MTK)
 - Steering group meetings
 - Webinar: CE in agriculture, marketplace presented 23.10.2024 (MTK)
5. We make transition! In the project public authorities work on social and ecological initiatives with civil society, and co-create changes in the areas of consumption, mobility, energy and social life.
 - Agricultural Arenas in Hämeenkyrö 6.3.2024, 14.3.2024, 27.3.2024 and 26.3.2025.
 - Hämeenkyrö Innovation and Sustainability Group meetings 21.5.2024 (EKOF: Koivisto)
6. KIERTOTRE-project (BT), rigid plastics collection pilot (companies) Q4/2023, synergies with TREASoURcE rigid plastics collection pilot (consumers) (WP2, WP3, WP6)
7. BePS – biogas project in Pirkanmaa and Satakunta region
 - Participation to biogas day at Jokioinen 2.6.2024 (MTK)
 - Meeting: policy recommendations 26.9.2024 (MTK, EKOF)
 - Collaboration meetings to plan joint events (EKOF)
 - Biogas events organized jointly in Hämeenkyrö on 26.11.2024 and in Ikaalinen 24.1.2025 (EKOF: Koivisto, MTK: Berglund)
8. BioDemo – project promoting side stream utilization
 - Meetings: 20.5.2024, 2.9.2024, 6.11.2024, 21.1.2025, 24.3.2025 (MTK, EKOF)
9. RuokoLog – project about reed utilization – aiming to build marketplace for reed
 - Meetings: 11.10.2024, 22.11.2024, 14.1.2025 and 22.4.2025 (MTK, EKOF)
10. BalticReed – project about reed utilization
 - Meetings: 2.10.2024 and 14.1.2025 (MTK)
11. Hortianna project: side streams from horticulture
 - Meetings: 7.10.2024 (MTK, EKOF)
 - Participation to side stream seminar 12.2.2025 (MTK)
 - Participation to webinars 6.3. and 13.3.2025 (MTK)
12. Pumaska – wood waste utilization project
 - Meetings: 12.8.2024 and 6.2.2024 (MTK, EKOF)
13. KiDi – circular economy project in Satakunta operating Sivuvirtapörssi marketplace
 - Meetings: 2.4.2024 and 23.10.2024 (MTK)

14. DigiBiogasHubs – biogas project developing a digital marketplace for biogas
 - Meetings 16.10.2024, 7.11.2024 and 28.11.2024 (MTK)
15. KeKeMa – webinar presentation about marketplace 11.3.2025 (MTK)
16. Pulina -project about sewage sludge utilization
 - Meeting 31.1.2024 (MTK)
 - Distribution of their questionnaires on sewage sludge -based fertilizers (MTK)
17. PAPILLONS EU Horizon – project on agricultural plastics
 - Workshops: 25.10.2024 and 21.3.2025 (MTK)
18. DeliSoil EU Horizon – project about recycled fertilizers
 - Workshop attendance and presentation about marketplace 29.1.2025 (MTK)
19. Location Innovation Hub, LIH
 - Meeting 15.12.2023 (MTK)
 - Collaboration on workshop for rural-urban symbiosis (MTK, FRSTD, EKOF)
 - Participation to workshop “New uses of spatial information” 4.9.2024 (MTK)
 - Media article about marketplace published in Positio by LIH (MTK)
20. HE PRIMUS
 - Collaboration webinar on LCA and system dynamics 25.4.2024 (GD, CLIC)
21. HE Engage4BIO
 - Collaboration on influencer campaign to raise awareness on sustainable packaging and sorting in Finland, February-October 2024 (CLIC)
 - Co-organization of a workshop on consumer engagement and citizen science methods regarding sustainable packaging 14.1.2025 (CLIC)
22. 4R open innovation ecosystem, Finland
 - Collaboration on influencer campaign to raise awareness on sustainable packaging and sorting in Finland, February-October 2024 (CLIC)
 - Co-organization of a workshop on consumer engagement and citizen science methods regarding sustainable packaging 14.1.2025 (CLIC)
23. HE RISE
 - Pitch event attendance as part of the 2024 EU Raw Materials Week to present the Circular batteries KVC 11.12.2024 (CLIC)
24. HE CARE – Circular Households
 - Collaboration on the joint CCRI projects video, March-May 2025 (CLIC)
 - Collaboration in Tampere region with repair café in SWAP! event 18.-19.10.2024 and in Finnish Craft & Design Fair 15.-17.11.2024 (EKOF)
25. Joint event 16.1.2025 with SIX Power project: Electrical energy storage solutions as investments discussion
26. Joint CCRI video with CircleUp project

Collaboration with other networks and associations in P2:

1. Biomass Atlas (WP5)
2. Co-operation with Finnish Biocycle and Biogas Association (WP5)
3. Co-operation with ProAgraria (WP5)
4. Co-operation with LAG Pohjois-Satakunta (WP5)
5. ECO3 (WP3, WP5, WP6)
6. Circular Economy Green Deal Finland (several meetings 2022-2023) (MTK, Kärki, BT, Ete-läaho)
7. Centre for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment (WP5)
8. Gaia-X Finland – Circular Economy domain working group

9. MTK unions (WP5)
10. Circular Economy Finland (KiSu) (WP5)
11. Climate network Pirkanmaa (WP5)

In addition, several other cities, municipalities and regions and their local stakeholders have been collaborated with outside the CCRI network:

1. Tartu (Estonia)
2. Tallinn (Estonia)
3. Riga (Latvia)
4. Kaunas (Lithuania)
5. Warsaw (Poland)
6. Lempäälä (Finland)
7. Turku (Finland)
8. Salo (Finland)
9. Forssa (Finland)
10. Hämeenkyrö (Finland)
11. Mänttä-Vilppula (Finland)
12. Orivesi (Finland)
13. Urjala (Finland),
14. Satakunta region (Finland)
15. Jyväskylä region (Finland)
16. Sotkamo (Finland)
17. Häme region (Finland)
18. Kongsberg (Norway)
19. Flå (Norway)
20. Indre Østfold (Norway)
21. Rakkestad (Norway)
22. Spydeberg (Norway)
23. Marker (Norway)
24. Nordre Follo (Norway)
25. Lier (Norway)
26. Ringerike (Norway)
27. Vestby (Norway)
28. Drammenv (Norway)
29. Nittedal (Norway)
30. Bærum (Norway)
31. Aurskog-Høland (Norway)
32. Nannestad (Norway)

4. Policy recommendations

In TREASoURcE, all project activities are considered to contribute to data gathering or generation, new knowledge, identification of gaps and barriers and development of possible solutions and ideas to overcome identified gaps and barriers. Policy recommendations are generated on different levels when relevant – local, regional, national and EU level.

Task 1.3 of the TREASoURcE project aimed to map the EU and national regulatory frameworks and generate policy recommendations to overcome regulatory barriers and enable circularity in three key value chains: plastics, EV batteries, and bio-based side and waste streams. This work culminated in deliverable D1.3 "Legislative and regulatory framework for target value chains", submitted in June 2024, which presents a comprehensive analysis of both binding and non-binding policy instruments across the EU, with national-level assessments for Finland, Estonia, and Norway. The process involved identifying relevant policy instruments, analysing their content, and systematically mapping regulatory drivers and barriers using structured working sheets. Validation of findings and co-development of recommendations were achieved through four stakeholder workshops held between February and May 2024. These included three dedicated sessions for each value chain (plastics, bio-based side and waste streams, EV batteries), involving representatives from industry, municipalities, academia, and NGOs.

Notably, the final workshop, held on 13 May 2024, focused specifically on engaging EU-level policy-makers under the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative. This online session brought together CCRI policy officers and aimed to critically review the identified policy gaps and recommendations from a regulatory and implementation perspective. The participation of CCRI representatives provided an opportunity to align TREASoURcE's outputs with the EU's broader circular economy ambitions and allowed direct feedback from those actively shaping policy at the European Commission level. Insights gathered from all workshops informed the refinement of 16 policy recommendations (8 for plastics, 5 for batteries, 3 for bio-based value chains), addressing topics such as eco-design, traceability, recycled content, safety and quality standards, and incentive mechanisms.

A dedicated policy recommendation session was also held during the TREASoURcE consortium meeting in Tallinn on 11 June 2024, where project partners collaboratively reviewed and finalized the recommendations to be translated into policy briefs. Based on this multidisciplinary input, responsibility for the development of briefs was allocated to VTT (plastics), SINTEF (batteries), and MTK (bio-based side and waste stream). The first policy brief—on Finnish biogas incentives—was published in January 2025, receiving broad dissemination via media, stakeholder outreach, and a roundtable co-organized by eight Finnish associations in March 2025. Policy briefs on batteries and plastics are currently under development.

In Work Package 2, part of the stakeholder engagement demonstrations is the CE wise procurement activities. The policy recommendations will be done in collaboration with WP1 and WP2 as well as the KVC WPs (WP3-WP5). WP2 will also contribute to local and regional policy implementation to advance the circular economy. This includes collaboration with the Østfold region on climate-smart procurement to support the development of biogas and circular plastics policies. Circular economy policy recommendations will be developed for three regional plans, covering a total of 51 municipalities.

WP4's Deliverable D4.1 – "Existing and Upcoming Challenges for Extending Electric Vehicle Battery Lifetime" provides policy recommendations to accelerate second-life battery uptake in stationary energy systems, based on ten key challenges across technical, regulatory, eco-design, and safety areas. These recommendations are also included in a [peer-reviewed scientific paper](#), supporting strategies for battery repair, reuse, repurposing, and recycling, underpinned by clear regulations, ecodesign principles, and safety standards, to advance circular battery use and sustainable energy transitions.

In summary, TREASoURcE has contributed to the development of several policy recommendations during Period 2.

- WP1:
 - Deliverable D1.3 completed, providing in total 16 policy recommendations to support circularity in key value chains.
 - Plastics: 8 recommendations on eco-design, traceability, and recycled content.
 - EV batteries: 5 recommendations on reuse, safety, and material flows.
 - Bio-based side and waste streams: 3 recommendations on incentives and sustainability standards.
 - Policy brief on Finnish biogas incentives produced (MTK-led), Finnish and English versions are available online.
 - KVC-specific policy briefs for batteries and plastics are under preparation; cross-WP collaboration in place for dissemination.
- WP2:
 - Collaboration with Østfold region on climate-smart procurement to support biogas and circular plastic policy development.
 - Circular economy policy recommendations developed for 3 regional plans across 51 municipalities.
- WP4:
 - Policy recommendations published in D4.1 and a journal article on accelerating second-life battery uptake in stationary energy systems.
- WP5:
 - Policy brief on biogas incentives in Finland published in January 2025, based on findings from D1.3.

The work towards further policy brief formulation for plastic and battery, and its dissemination is ongoing and will be published in upcoming periods.

5. REFERENCES

European Commission. (2023). *Circular Cities and Regions Initiative*. Retrieved from <https://circular-cities-and-regions.ec.europa.eu/about>